

Growing the Football Game: The Increasing Economic and Social Relevance of Older Fans and Those with Disabilities in the European Football Industry

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Pre-print and accepted to be published at Soccer and Society

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/14660970.2014.920623>

Abstract

In trying to grow the customer base of the football game, recent studies have argued that relevant key actors in the European football industry such as football governing bodies and professional clubs must attend to the needs of all their supporters as well as consider the economic and social relevance of older supporters and those with disabilities, described as the ‘new’ generation of sport customers. Through analysis of major trends in legislation, demography, consumer expenditures, and sport and leisure interests over time, coupled with a series of interviews with representatives of three of the main football leagues in Europe, this article contends that these two growing segments of sport consumers should be valued as important stakeholders, with enhanced access to all types of services, goods and experiences, not only considered a legal and moral imperative but one which also makes good business sense. To attend the needs of these two groups of supporters will not only create managerial challenges but also significant opportunities for sustainable business growth that the football industry cannot underestimate as they seek to activate this latent consumer demand. Improving access to stadia is also a timely issue that football clubs should integrate into their organization’s culture and operations in order to provide an inclusive environment at club level.

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Introduction

The success of global sport organizations relies upon identifying the profile of existing and prospective customers and effectively meeting their needs and expectations. As the current chairman of UEFA (the governing body of European football), Michel Platini, clearly stated, fans are considered major stakeholders in football. ‘Supporters are the lifeblood at the very heart of professional football. Without its supporters, professional football would not be very different from an amateur sport or pastime’.¹ Similar sentiments can be found in the mission statements of many European football leagues² and professional football clubs. In the same way, the UEFA has made explicit reference to the importance of increasing the fan base of the football game by treating fans with disabilities as valuable customers based on their large economic impact. According to UEFA ‘disabled people should therefore be seen as valued customers, with good access not only as a moral issue but also as good business sense’.³

Ageing coupled with disability has become a major demographic trend worldwide. The latest statistics have revealed that large sections of the population within the European Union’s 28 countries⁴ have a variety of disabilities⁵ and also the population is getting older⁶ (see table 1). This suggests that such large numbers of potential football consumers could have a multiplier effect as older people and those with disabilities are able to influence their relatives, friends, and caregivers who often accompany them to leisure and sporting events. As the European Commission and the recent Census from the UK, Germany and Spain data supports, the share of people with disabilities and the older population is not only increasing quickly, but most importantly it will continue to rise in the next five decades.⁷ This data provides anecdotal evidence that this market

segment is worthy of attention by the football industry and other related industry sectors.⁸ As the general population ages, people develop age-related disabilities. Obviously, this demographic growth has created challenges as well as significant opportunities for sustainable business growth that the European football industry can no longer underestimate as they seek to activate this latent demand in the upcoming decades. As in other related industry sectors, this article contends that Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)⁹ demands that relevant stakeholders in the European football industry, such as national governing bodies as well as professional clubs, should respond to the needs and expectations of all their customers, including people with disabilities and older people.

Understanding Football Stadia and Inclusivity

Over the past decade, research into understanding the sport and leisure habits, needs and consumer expenditures of individuals and groups represents an important area of study within the sport management field worldwide.¹⁰ Similarly, past studies in the area of football and inclusivity, as this special issue seeks to address, have not devoted sufficient attention to understanding the main characteristics and demands from individuals with disabilities and older people as consumers and spectators. Both groups are increasingly deemed important subsets of football consumers; that is, while attending football matches is recognized as one of the most popular forms of leisure activities worldwide,¹¹ analysis of the economic and social relevance of these two ‘new’ market segments as well as analyzing the connection (and similarities) between these two groups of sport consumers is still an under-researched area, both for the football industry and the sport management sector.

Much of the academic literature on the European football industry has focused on diverse economic, sociological, and managerial themes, such as the development of clubs and their stadia,¹² the relationships and level of representation of football fans within their clubs as part of the governance of European clubs,¹³ the level of attendance of football fans to their stadia¹⁴ or the social profile of fans who attend live matches at large venues. Other areas of interest have included the commercial opportunities found in postmodern stadia, given that these facilities rely on extending their operations throughout the whole year and not just during the traditional football calendar.¹⁵ Therefore, contemporary stadia are now expected to draw large audiences, including older fans and those with disabilities, by offering all types of services, goods and experiences on match and non-match days. As a consequence, managers are developing new strategies to make stadia appeal to wider audiences, such as offering VIP experiences and including more entertainment features in their stadia as part of the sport experience. However, few studies in sport management have explored the implementation of stadium policies in order to provide a high-quality experience for customers with disabilities attending events at European stadia.¹⁶ Moreover, improving access for fans with disabilities and older fans in European football stadia still remains a managerial challenge for most European clubs. As Phil Downs, one of the pioneers in this area and former chairman and co-founder of the National Association of Disabled Supporters (NADS) (renamed Level Playing Field since 2011) and currently in charge of the operations for all Manchester United events and services for disabled fans at Old Trafford Stadium said, ‘improving the accessibility to stadia in most European football clubs should be one of the main concern of the next decade’.¹⁷ More recent scholarship has analyzed access for all types of users, including the needs and demands of

individuals with disabilities, when they plan to attend a sporting event in European stadia¹⁸ and in U.S. stadia,¹⁹ and has examined the level of accommodations for spectators with disabilities in European stadia.

In general, many practitioners and academics still view the provision of universal accessibility at large sports venues as an imperative based on non-economic motivations, most notably ethical, legal and social justifications, rather than based mainly on economic reasons.²⁰ To extend this argument, there is also a paucity of studies in this area of sport management scholarship that present sufficient evidence of a strong business case of this growing segment market at football leagues and clubs in Europe.²¹ As part of this claim, studies conducted in Europe and in the United States have argued that the sport industry must address the needs and requirements of this important subset of sport consumers.

In this paper, we contend that improving access in stadia in most European football clubs for spectators with disabilities and older people should become a strategic priority for governing bodies and individual football clubs. Downs appeals to the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) efforts of football clubs. Commenting on the successful experience of Manchester United, he remarked:

...we need to generate awareness within football not only in England but also in European clubs to improve their stadium facilities considering the social aspects that accessibility produce.²²

Football clubs can provide total inclusion within their stadium operations and CSR actions at the club level through common-sense solutions, such as the provision of an ‘Ability Suite’ which provides a comfortable (and fully accessible) place for disabled supporters and older supporters and their companions to gather at Old Trafford Stadium on match and non-match days.

Increasingly, as accessibility has become a major political issue for UEFA, some European Leagues such as the Premier League and Bundesliga and some individual clubs, notably Manchester United, Arsenal, Manchester City or Bayern Munich, have approached the promotion and implementation of accessibility and disability as part of their organization’s culture and everyday business operations.²³ However, there are still a number of physical barriers to stadium accessibility but also a notable resistance by senior and middle managers to the implementation of actions and policies that facilitate individuals with disabilities attending matches regularly at stadia and enjoying the same experience as the rest of able-bodied spectators.²⁴ One of the reasons that might explain this resistance from upper level managers to the implementation of an inclusive business environment, as Scott-Parker and Zadek clearly contend in the United Kingdom, is that:

... most managers, including many in public sector and non-profit organizations, remain unconvinced that people with disabilities can enhance their overall business performance.²⁵

As a result, there is a concomitant underestimation of the significance of disabled people as an emerging and recognizable customer group and a lack of attention to the older market, described as the ‘new old market of the early twenty first century’, as Luker and Stone claim based on the U.S. sport industry. In particular, Luker reinforced this lack of attention by calling for action to attend the needs of older fans considering that most of the U.S. sport industry focuses on fans between the ages of 18 and 34, while a large number of loyal and avid fans are those aged over 35.²⁶ There is a need to identify and understand the characteristics of those sport customer groups that bring the greatest economic and social value to the sport industry. In this article, the following recommendation by Scott-Parker and Zadek is adapted:

...it is critically important to understand why organisations remain unconvinced [of a sound business case for older fans and fans with disabilities].²⁷ Once these reasons are understood, they can be addressed by people with disabilities and their advocates.

As one of the aims of the study, researchers seek to provide sufficient indicators that might contribute to convince relevant key actors of the European football industry, such as CEOs, club managers, and officials, that meeting effectively the demands of these growing generations of consumers in the football industry as one that makes good business sense. This will contribute to overcome some of the misconceptions that prevent managers to promote inclusive environments as football stadia:

The challenge is therefore to present arguments that go beyond short-term cost-benefit analyses and to describe a long-term strategic case integrated into the broader diversity perspective: it is essential to simultaneously address the

ignorance and fear that currently prevent potential business benefits from being realized.²⁸

Building the Business Case for Inclusivity

This paper builds the ‘business case for inclusivity’ by combining economic, social and sporting indicators that include: a) current and upcoming demographic trends of people with disabilities and older adults within all EU member states; b) sport and leisure interests for older adults and those with disabilities; c) social composition and levels of attendance to football matches in stadia of the three football leagues considered in our analysis (English Premier League, Bundesliga and Spanish Primera Liga); d) the spending power of those groups; and e) the relationships and level of representation of those fans with their clubs and football governing bodies.

Method

This exploratory study draws on both primary and secondary sources. Primary data was collected by means of in-depth semi-structured interviews with six key stakeholders in three of the most prestigious football professional leagues in Europe. These leagues were selected based on sporting performance, financial performance, level of attendance and level of provision for fans with disabilities to their clubs’ stadia over recent years. Four relevant Disability Liaison Officers of Premier League and Bundesliga clubs were also interviewed and were followed up by ongoing personal communications via email or Skype from early 2008 to January 2014. The analysis also included personal observations at the stadia as well as the long-time experience and knowledge of Phil Downs, based on over 20 years of experience at one of the world’s largest football clubs

and responsible for the accessibility operation of Manchester United's Old Trafford Stadium.

These two data collection processes enhanced the level of analysis and helped to bridge the gap between theory and practice. Parallel to this original data collection, documentary analysis was conducted using documents produced from the European Commission and European countries, European and national Census, different European (UEFA) and national football governing bodies (Premier League, Bundesliga and Spanish Professional League), advocacy organizations of fans with disabilities (Centre for Access to Football in Europe (CAFÉ), Level Playing Field and BBAG (Bundesbehindertenfanarbeitsgemeinschaft), National (English) Fans Surveys (Premier League) and football clubs from our three target leagues. Analysis of these documents offers comprehensive and reliable statistics about the profile and characteristics of older people and those with disabilities as spectators and consumers. Furthermore, additional evidence from newspapers, official and unofficial reports and club websites have been relevant to building and documenting the argument that the two market segments make a good business case to the European football industry.

Findings

Demographic Trends of People with Disabilities and Older People in Europe

Demographic trends such as ageing and people with disabilities have a substantial economic impact on the sport and leisure industry in general and on the football industry in particular. The latest statistics show that ageing within the European Union's

28 state members is a reality. Overall, the number of older people has increased exponentially over the last decades in Europe. Generally, the EU's population was estimated at 506.8 m. people as of 1 January 2012. Of these people, there were about 185 m. aged 50 and over which represent about 36.9 percent of the total population²⁹ (see Table 1). Apart from this, Eurostat population projections 'foresee that the number of people over 60 years will increase by about two million persons per year in the coming decades'.³⁰ These figures will substantially increase when people with disabilities are also included. The European Commission itself estimates there are more than 80 m. people with disabilities in Europe, representing about 15 percent of the population.³¹ Together both segments of population represent more than 50 percent of the population.

This study focused on three countries: the United Kingdom, Germany and Spain. In the U.K., the Department of Work and Pensions recently calculated that there are almost 12 m. people with disabilities, which include those with a limiting long-term illness, impairment and disability.³² In addition, two U.K. governing bodies, the Office for Disability Issues and the Office for National Statistics, concur in estimating that there are currently 19 m. people aged 60 or over, a figure which is projected to rise to 22.5 m. by 2020.³³ Unlike the United Kingdom, the German Federal Statistics Office (*Statistisches Bundesamt*) only recognizes people with severe disabilities, excluding a wide variety of types of disabilities. Bearing this criteria in mind, the overall number of people with severe disabilities has increased from 7,101,682 in 2009 to 7,289,173 in 2011 (Statistisches Bundesamt officer, personal communication, November 4 2012) which represents an increase of 2.6 percent. However, the number of people with

different types of disabilities in Germany would be larger. Focusing on those people aged 50 and over in Germany, the figure accounts for 30 percent of the overall population. In Spain, despite difficulties to obtain reliable and current data on the number and type of people with disabilities, the Spanish Statistics Institute (*Instituto Nacional de Estadística*) showed that there were almost 4 million disabled people in 2008, representing around 9 percent of Spain's overall population.³⁴ The 2011 Census estimated the Spanish population is growing increasingly older considering that life expectancy exceeded 82 years old, with the population aged over 64 accounting for 17.3 percent of the Spanish population.

The share of individuals with disabilities and older people significantly it will continue to rise over the next five decades.³⁵ As Ahtonen and Pardo stressed³⁶, Eurostat predicts that by 2060 the number of people aged 65 and over in the European Union will have increased to around 30 percent. Already, over 32 percent of those aged between 55 and 65 years report a disability and this figure increases to over 40 percent, 60 percent and 70 percent respectively for each additional decade.³⁷

Table 1 near here

While there are obvious limitations within these figures in that there are differences in the criteria used to estimate the number of people with disabilities and older people within the European Union, there is still a strong sense when considering that one in four Europeans has a family member with a disability and six out of ten Europeans have a disabled person within their circle of friends, colleagues and relatives.

Sport and Leisure Interests for Older People and Those with Disabilities

A second common indicator of the economic and social relevance of older fans and those with disabilities focuses on analysis of the level of participation of our target groups in sport and leisure activities, such as attending matches at stadia. One of the challenges that different studies and advocacy organizations concur in identifying is how to quantify the number of European individuals with disabilities as well as older people attending those matches. In this aspect, the level of accessibility at stadia in Europe can be ultimately a major facilitator or barrier to increasing the number of people from both market segments that attend matches at those venues. As noted by Grady and Paramio-Salcines³⁸, a recent study commissioned by UEFA found that 33 percent of people with disabilities do not attend the matches because the facilities are not accessible to them. Somewhat surprisingly, the PanEuropean advocacy organization CAFÉ³⁹ estimated that:

...around 50 percent of people with disabilities have never attended a sporting or public event and at least one third of disabled Europeans have never travelled abroad or even participated in day excursions because of inaccessible venues and services.

Although there is no similar data about participation of older people at football matches, the *Taking Part survey* evidence for England shows, as Taylor⁴⁰ remarked, some aspects that might be relevant for different stakeholders, in that ‘attending historic sites, arts events, museums and galleries, and for gambling, participation rates increase until

middle age, then fall with older age'. What is more relevant to this study is that age is one of the main influences on sport and leisure participation and is a major challenge to sport and leisure managers. But as this study concurs with the evidence from the adult leisure time in Spain in 2010,⁴¹ older people are one of the groups with more disposable time (and income) for leisure activities such as attending matches at stadia.

Levels of Attendance and Social Composition in Football Matches in England, Germany, and Spain

Despite the fact that not all individuals with disabilities and older population in Europe are football fans⁴², an initial conservative estimation by the advocacy organization CAFE considers that there are approximately 500,000 people with disabilities who are deemed to be football fans with a growing number of them who regularly attend, either alone or accompanied, matches at European stadia as one of their preferred leisure activities.

After examining the level of attendance of football matches in our target football leagues clubs' stadia (summarized in table 2), it is worth noticing that attendances to German Bundesliga 1 clubs' stadia totaled the remarkable figure of 13.8 m. spectators in the 2011-12 season,⁴³ which represented a 5.2 percent increase compared to the 2010-11 season (with an overall attendance of 12.8 m.). Premier League clubs' stadia also attracted similar overall figures to the Bundesliga. According to Richard Scudamore, Chief Executive of the Premier League, 'our clubs deserve great credit for a range of supporters' initiatives that brought 13.6 m. supporters through the turnstiles

last season (2011/12) producing a record stadium capacity of 95.3 percent'.⁴⁴ However, as one representative of the Spanish Liga de Fútbol Profesional noted, the Primera Division's attendance in the 2012-13 season decreased slightly to 9.6 m. spectators, compared to the 9.9 m. spectators in the 2011-12 season (LFP officer, personal communication, January 2014).

Table 2 near here

When trying to understand the type and demographic profile of fans that attend football matches at those Leagues' stadia and how professional leagues value individuals with disabilities⁴⁵ and older people as spectators, we found that the Premier League⁴⁶ clearly focused on attracting youngsters, families and ethnic minorities to the football game saying that '19% of those who attended the 2011/12 season were fans aged 18-24 years (12% of the population is in this age range), 13% of season tickets holders are children, 23% of match fans are women and 12% are ethnic minorities, while 41 is the average age of an adult fan going to matches'. In addition, the Premier League targeted families when half of fans (51%) attend matches with friends, 20% with their spouses, and 34% with other family members; 29% attended with children.

In the case of the Deutsche Football League (DFL) in 2009 it was estimated that '*out of 800,000 wheelchair users living in Germany, 30,400 are interested in football*' (M. Rühmann, personal communication, December 18 2009). Nevertheless, the Bundesliga itself as a governing body does not have accurate figures on the number of fans with

disabilities and older fans that regularly attend matches at Bundesliga stadia. As one of the current DFL officer confirms to us:

...the Deutsche Football League (DFL) does not collect this data, only the clubs themselves might be able to evaluate the access of their fans. Most of them do have an electronic access control, but no club has and even with the access control you can normally evaluate the different categories but not the whole personal data....For home games the advance ticket offices as well as the box-offices usually sell the tickets without recording personal data (personal communication, December 10 2013).

At the time of writing, the English advocacy group Level Playing Field (LPF)⁴⁷ estimated that there are more than 30,000 people with disabilities actively attending matches regularly in England and Wales. At club level, Manchester United has implemented a wide range of accessibility services and programmes for individuals with disabilities at Old Trafford Stadium. This long-term commitment has been a central part of their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) policy. As a result, the club estimates that over 2,200 people with disabilities, which also include some companions, are able to access football matches and enjoy similar services, activities and experiences as the rest of their large fan base.⁴⁸

In contrast to their English and German counterparts, these numbers are reduced considerably when considering the level of provision and operation of Spanish stadia.⁴⁹ In a 2008 study, which analyzed the existing facilities and services available for fans with disabilities and their companions on match days by six Spanish Primera Division

clubs' stadia, it was found that, in general, except in two stadia like La Nueva Condomina, Real Murcia or Santiago Bernabeu, Real Madrid, there were an inadequate number of seats for fans with disabilities in stadia. Most of the accessible features and services were for wheelchair users, but there was a complete lack of provision for the visually impaired, people with ambulatory disabilities or other types of disabilities as happens at Bundesliga and Premier League stadia. Despite these poor conditions, it was estimated that more than thirty disabled fans plus their companions still regularly attend each match.⁵⁰ Yet, it is still unknown how many more follow the league's matches on television or via print or electronic media. The representative of the Spanish Liga Profesional clearly stated that 'the LFP does not have any data on fans with disabilities and older fans attending to clubs' stadia' (LFP officer, personal communication, January 20 2014). In 2013, FC Barcelona attempted to quantify the number of fans with different disabilities within their fan base. In their study, the club estimated that there are 4,051 members with a broad range of disabilities, where over 2,000 fans (2.170) are wheelchair users, followed by sensory (hearing and vision) (1.850) and learning (difficulties) (31) disabilities.⁵¹ Despite these numbers, the level of provision of seats for fans with disabilities at the FC Barcelona Stadium, Camp Nou, is at the time of writing extremely poor (only 40 seats for wheelchair fans) considering the overall capacity estimated at 98,784 compared to other clubs in Spain and even worse compared with European football stadia generally.⁵²

The empirical data presented shows that there is no consistently available data which has considered both market segments over time. In the same way, older fans and fans with disabilities as spectators in Europe have been ignored by those Leagues and their

clubs, with some relevant exceptions, in favour of other groups such as youngsters, families and other minorities.

Spending Power of People with Disabilities and Older People

Another critical indicator of sport and leisure's importance in society is spending by consumers.⁵³ Focusing on this economic indicator, in the last two decades, average spending per household in the UK on leisure services has doubled in real terms⁵⁴ and leisure spending is typically around 27 percent of total consumer spending in the UK. Similarly, and drawing on general official statistics, the Office for Disability Issues⁵⁵ concurs with the Level Playing Field (LPF)⁵⁶ to state that disabled people in the UK nowadays have over £80 bn. a year available to spend on goods and services. In addition, this organization offers other appealing figures saying that disabled customers may account for up to 20 percent of the customer base for an average UK business. Beyond Europe, the Americans with Disabilities 2010 and the U.S. Department of Justice offer also much more compelling figures than the UK's case on the economic impact of people with disabilities and older people. For the first group, it is estimated that this group make up a significant market of consumers, representing more than \$200 bn. a year available to spend on goods and services⁵⁷, while the economic impact of older people is also quite significant after the U.S. Department of Justice clearly stated that 'more than 50% of the total U.S. discretionary income is controlled by those 50 years and older. This is not a market that businesses should turn away from their doors'.⁵⁸

When analyzing the spending power of either fans with disabilities or older fans, Level Playing Field only focused on people with disabilities; they do not analyze the economic spending of older fans. Meanwhile, the other two leagues have not attempted to estimate the economic power of people with disabilities in general or fans with disabilities in particular. As the DFL's representative confirmed to us the lack of data on the spending power of football fans with disabilities and older fans in Germany by saying:

We do not have data on this issue. Maybe some of the clubs (who are working with registered cashless card systems) have some data. But I am not sure if any club has evaluated the spending power of those two groups yet (personal communication, December 10 2013).

Football Governing Bodies and Professional Football Club Policies for Older Fans and Those with Disabilities

As previously published⁵⁹, within the football industry, the Premier League and the Bundesliga were the first to establish guidelines and policies to try to address the needs of people with disabilities. Meanwhile, the Spanish Professional Football League has not issued any specific guidelines or policies to address the needs and expectations of fans with disabilities. Additionally, the best documents to guide anyone with the design, planning and operation come from the US (Accessible Guidelines for Stadia and Arenas 2004 and Tickets Sales 2011) and also from Europe (Accessible Stadia Guide 2004 and the UEFA and CAFE 'Good Practice Guide to Creating an Accessible Stadium and Matchday Experience').

Concluding Remarks and Managerial Implications for Clubs and Football Governing Bodies in Europe

As in other industry sectors like retail, hospitality and tourism and leisure and culture that have gradually started treating people with disabilities like valued customers, the current investigation represents an initial exploration of the analysis of the economic and social importance of older people and those with disabilities as spectators of stadia within three of the main football leagues in Europe.

When evaluating the potential of the two market segments for the football industry, the current and future demographic projections make this an attractive market for sustainable growth. This market has now expanded to over 258 m. people (including people with disabilities and older people) in Europe. This data as well as the additional indicators discussed above demonstrate that these market segments are clearly deserving of management's attention which should include the prospect of additional resources being directed to providing a superior sport experience or at least a base level experience equivalent to that which other fans receive.

Another factor that supports the relevance of these combined market segments as customers is the fact that they have well-defined sport and leisure interests forming part of their everyday consumer spending. It is the confluence of the demographic shift, the sport and leisure interests, their leisure time available, and the consumer spending that now make these even more attractive market segments for European football clubs.

Clearly our target populations are not necessarily all football fans, although there is a growing number of fans with disabilities and older fans regularly attending stadia in Europe, whether alone or accompanied by friends or family. Data from the main football leagues in Europe shows that this number is steadily increasing, except for a slight decline in attendance at Spanish Professional League stadia. This increase in consumer demand naturally extends to these two market segments.

In light of these factors, the relevant stakeholders of European leagues and clubs like the CEO's, club managers, and officials are forced into thinking how to demonstrate organizational commitment, overcoming the traditional and long-term resistance, to the implementation of specific policy actions capable of meeting the needs of all supporters which justifiably now include the combined market segments of disabled and older people. Universal accessibility become the key to implementation of such policies and will ultimately enhance the customer experience of these fans.

The challenge for managers and marketers has always been a combination of meeting effectively the needs and expectations of this growing demographic as well as attempting to broaden the appeal of the venues' physical characteristics in order to retain this segment of customer base and create opportunities for an extended period of increase by this market segment in the football industry. We are still at this early stage of understanding and appreciating the emergence of this growing demographic of disabled and older people visiting stadia, which has been characterized by a process of

‘ad hoc’ development in producing a coping strategy to meet current needs. As we look forward toward the middle stage of development, the challenge will become considering and developing a much more structured approach that is capable of addressing the needs of this market segment in respect of the existing customer base as well as the projected expansion of the future customer base.

Ideas to overcome resistance, as Scott-Parker and Zadek have previously argued, include upper and middle managers implementing inclusive environments at clubs’ stadia and organizations. It is now essential that upper and middle managers and senior stakeholders begin the process of understanding the characteristics of this market segment. They need to connect with these groups and integrate their feedback and experiences which will then assist in defining the new criteria needed to produce desired future enhancements. This could prove to show that further consideration needs to be given to potential changes to physical characteristics which impact the level of accessibility of the stadium. Many ideas can be brought into the sphere of consideration when thinking of how we move forward with our attempts to enhance our services for fans. Changes to the physical characteristics of some parts of the stadium and possibly extending our thinking to re-imagine the immediate areas around the stadium and considering better options in respect to parking areas, transport links and connection between the two now become top priorities.

There is no doubt that disability increases with age, making it true to say that there is a definite ‘squeeze’ on the stadium event staff involved in an stadium operation context

when dealing with this demographic. This situation has led Phil Downs to describe the successful approach Manchester United has used to appeal to this new generation of sport customers:

...Many years ago, we accepted that the average age of our fans was going to steadily increase as the official statistics show. We also acknowledge that a football stadium environment is not normally one of the easiest to negotiate if you have any kind of mobility difficulty. Hence, we have already taken steps to increase the overall numbers of accessible parking bays. At one time, the number of people with walking difficulties trying to get to a standard seat was so small that they could walk up to the stadium and ask to use the lift without any problem. That is not the case now. We have a tried and trusted structure for accommodating supporters such that those who need this consideration no longer have to worry about whether or not their particular need will be provided for them (personal communication, 30 September 2013).

Mounting evidence shows that we are moving into an epoch where companies must concentrate more of their efforts on expanding their customer base to include an increasing number of people with disabilities (including those with severe difficulties) and older people. Finally, European governing bodies and football clubs need to commit additional resources to better understand the number of fans with disabilities and older fans that attend matches regularly at European clubs' stadia as well as the customer preferences of those groups. In addition, these governing bodies and clubs should start considering the needs of these two growing segments of sport consumers, as other related industry sectors, in order to increase their fan base, to promote inclusivity at the football sector as well as to provide a high-quality customer to all fans, including our two growing segments of fans.

Acknowledgements

This study is part of the research project entitled ‘Estudio Comparativo de las Funciones y Competencias del Experto en Accesibilidad Universal en Instalaciones y Eventos Deportivos: Perspectiva Norteamericana y Europea’ (*Comparative Study of the Role and Competencies of the Disability Liaison Office on Sport Facilities and Events: North American and European Perspective*) led by Dr. Juan L. Paramio-Salcines, Universidad Autonoma de Madrid with Dr. John Grady, University of South Carolina and funded by the Spanish Bank, Banco de Santander (2^a Convocatoria de Proyectos de Cooperación Interuniversitaria UAM-Banco de Santander con EEUU, 2013-2014).

¹ UEFAb. *Supporter Liaison Officer Handbook*, 3.

² See this statement in different football leagues such as Premier League, *Premier League Guidance for Clubs on Disabled Fans and Customers 2010; 2012/13 Premier League Season Review; Premier League Research and Insight Season 2011/12* ; Liga de Fútbol Profesional, *Memoria 2011-2012 Liga de Fútbol Profesional*; The Football League, *Supporters Survey 2010*; Bundesliga, *Bundesliga Report 2013*. See also Deloitte, *Fan Power Football Money League*.

³ UEFAa. *Access for All. UEFA and CAFÉ Good Practice Guide to Creating an Accessible Stadium and Matchday Experience*, 11. See a more detailed discussion on Paramio-Salcines and Kitchin, ‘Institutional Perspectives on the Implementation of Disability Legislation and Services for Spectators with Disabilities in European Professional Football’ and Grady and James, ‘Understanding the Needs of Spectators with Disabilities attending Sporting Events’.

⁴ At the time of writing, there are 28 countries within the European Union after the adhesion of Croatia on 1 July 2013.

⁵ To clarify the term disability will be important to locate this concept as part of the ongoing debate about the main perspectives concerning disability; the medical and social models. Based on both approaches, the term disability has different and distinctive meanings. On the light of this comment, disability can mean something entirely different in relation to football fans with disabilities, based on the medical and social models of disability. From the football industry, and as an advocacy group as the English Playing Field states, each club has a different approach to definition and qualification of disability and even between individuals within a club. For the purposes of this study, we follow what this advocacy group defines as a disabled supporter: ‘any person who, because of their disability or impairment, is unable to use ordinary stand seating without contravening Health and Safety Regulations, Guidelines or Policy OR where the club has provided a “reasonable adjustment or “auxiliary service” to enable that supporter to attend the venue. Any such person will be considered for use of the “designated areas” of the stadium in line with the procedures set out in this policy’ (Level Playing Field, 2013). See more details in Paramio-Salcines and Kitchin, ‘Institutional Perspectives on the Implementation of Disability Legislation and Services for Spectators with Disabilities in European Professional Football’.

⁶ For the purpose of this paper and considering that there is neither recognized statistical definition of ‘old’ or ‘older’ people (Eurostat 2010, 2012, 2013), though in their statistics, Eurostat starts measuring the number of older people as those people aged 50 and over, nor general consensus on who should be classed as old people we have defined in our study as those people over 50 years old as ‘older people’, considering that, at this age, the incidence of disability begins to increase significantly with this age. Different academics, practitioners and advocacy organizations have started to contend that the segment market of older people, known as the ‘grey market’ or ‘baby boomers’, and those with disabilities should be valued as two ‘new’ customer segments by the sport industry in general (see Stone, ‘The ‘New’ Older Market’; Luker, ‘Why Sport Industry must Recognize Importance of Older Fans’; Dolliver, ‘The Stats on Older Fans’; Wolfe, ‘Older Markets and the New Marketing Paradigm’ for a more detailed analysis of the US Sport Industry on the relevance of older people segment) and the football industry in Europe in particular (CAFÉ, ‘Annual Report 2011-2012’; Grady and Paramio-Salcines, ‘Global Approaches to Managing the Fan Experience for Patrons with Disabilities’; Downs and Paramio-Salcines, ‘Incorporating

Accessibility and Disability in the Manchester United Culture and Organization as part of their CSR policies'; Paramio-Salcines and Kitchin, 'Institutional Perspectives on the Implementation of Disability Legislation in Professional Football'; Waterman and Bell, *Disabled Access to Facilities* and Grady and James, 'Understanding the Needs of Spectators with Disabilities attending Sporting Events'.

⁷ See more details of this demographic trend in European countries, in Eurostat, *Demography Report 2010; Active Ageing and Solidarity between Generations; Basic Figures on the EU*. Office for National Statistics, *National Population Projections* for the UK; Federal Statistics Office, *Germany's Population by 2060* for Germany or Spanish Statistics Institute, *Spain in Figures 2013* for Spain. Beyond Europe, see Erickson, Lee and von Schrader. *2011 Disability Status Report. United States*; Brault. *American with Disabilities: 2010* and Werner. *The Older Population: 2010* to analyze this demographic trend and the large economic impact and social importance of our two segments of population in the United States.

⁸ Similar concerns for the travel industry are found in Hudson, 'Wooing Zoomers: Marketing to the Mature Traveler', hospitality (Grady and Ohlin) or sport (Grady and Paramio-Salcines; Grady and James).

⁹ Breitbarth and Harris. 'The Role of Corporate Social Responsibility in the Football Business. Towards the Development of a Conceptual Model'. Downs and Paramio-Salcines. 'Incorporating Accessibility and Disability in the Manchester United Culture and Organization as part of their CSR policies'; Walters and Tacon. 'Corporate Social Responsibility in European Football'. Walter and Kent. 'Do Fans Care? Assessing the Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility on Consumer Attitudes in the Sport Industry'.

¹⁰ To analyze the sport and leisure habits, needs and consumer expenditures of individuals and groups in European countries, see Taylor, *Torkildsen's Sport and Leisure Management* for the UK; Lera-López and Rapún-Gárate, 'Sports Participation versus Consumer Expenditure on Sport'; Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte, 'Anuario de Estadísticas Deportivas 2013'; Spanish Statistics Institute, *Spain in Figures 2013* for Spain; Pawlowski and Breuer, 'The Demand for Sport and Recreational Services' for Germany.

¹¹ In the 20th century, football became the national sport in many countries worldwide, with an estimated fan base over 3 bn. people. See Sartori, *European Stadium Insight 2011*, 6. However, these figures do not estimate the number of fans with disabilities and older fans.

¹² To analyze the relevance of the commercial development of the latest generation of stadia in Europe see Sartori. *European Stadium Insight 2011*; Paramio, Buraimo and Campos. 'From Modern to Postmodern' and Kitchin. 'Planning and Managing the Stadium Experience'.

¹³ See more details at Hassan and Hamil, 'Introduction: Models of Governance and Management in International Sport'; Giulianotti, 'Supporters, Followers, Fans and Flaneurs'; Cleland 'From Passive to Active: The Changing Relationship between Supporters and Football Clubs' and Llopis-Goig 'Propiedad y Gestión de los Clubes de Fútbol. La Perspectiva de los Aficionados'.

¹⁴ Premier League, *2012/13 Premier League Season Review; Premier League Research and Insight Season 2011/12*; The Football League, *Supporters Survey 2010*; Bundesliga, *Bundesliga Report 2013*.

¹⁵ See Sartori. *European Stadium Insight 2011* and Paramio, Buraimo and Campos. 'From Modern to Postmodern' and see more details of the case of Arsenal and the Emirates Stadium in Kitchin. 'Planning and Managing the Stadium Experience'.

¹⁶ Paramio-Salcines and Kitchin, 'Institutional Perspectives on the Implementation of Disability Legislation and Services for Spectators with Disabilities in European Professional Football'; Grady and Paramio-Salcines 'Global Approaches to Managing the Fan Experience for Patrons with Disabilities'; Grady and Paramio Salcines 'Global Disability Laws and their Impact on the Stadium Experience'; Kitchin 'Managing the Stadium Experience'; Grady and James, 'Understanding the Needs of Spectators with Disabilities attending Sporting Events'.

¹⁷ See Paramio, Buraimo and Campos, 'From Modern to Postmodern', 530.

¹⁸ Paramio, Campos and Buraimo, 'Promoting Accessibility for Fans with Disabilities to European Stadiums and Arenas'; Paramio-Salcines and Kitchin, 'Institutional Perspectives on the Implementation of Disability Legislation and Services for Spectators with Disabilities in European Professional Football'.

¹⁹ In the United States, see Grady and James, 'Understanding the Needs of Spectators with Disabilities attending Sporting Events'.

²⁰ As was reflected in Paramio, Campos and Buraimo (2011:385), 'Both individual clubs and governing bodies (in Europe) should become more proactive in the promotion of accessible stadia in decades to come. Those clubs that are still reactive and do not explore the benefits of dealing with providing good standards of accessibility within their stadia will be considered, as Downs states, as part of the problem rather than the solution, especially when some top clubs in Europe are moving forward on this issue'.

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- ²¹ Grady and Paramio-Salcines, 'Global Approaches to Managing the Fan Experience for Patrons with Disabilities'; Paramio, Campos and Buraimo, 'Promoting Accessibility for Fans with Disabilities to European Stadiums and Arenas'; Paramio-Salcines and Kitchin, 'Institutional Perspectives on the Implementation of Disability Legislation and Services for Spectators with Disabilities in European Professional Football'; Downs and Paramio-Salcines, 'Incorporating Accessibility and Disability in the Manchester United Culture and Organization as part of their CSR policies'.
- ²² See more details on Downs and Paramio-Salcines, 'Incorporating Accessibility and Disability in the Manchester United Culture and Organization as part of their CSR policies', 144.
- ²³ Downs and Paramio-Salcines, 'Incorporating Accessibility and Disability in the Manchester United Culture and Organization as part of their CSR policies'.
- ²⁴ This issue has been analysed on Grady and Paramio-Salcines, 'Global Approaches to Managing the Fan Experience for Patrons with Disabilities'; Paramio, Campos and Buraimo, 'Promoting Accessibility for Fans with Disabilities to European Stadiums and Arenas'; Paramio-Salcines and Kitchin, 'Institutional Perspectives on the Implementation of Disability Legislation and Services for Spectators with Disabilities in European Professional Football' and Grady and James, 'Understanding the Needs of Spectators with Disabilities attending Sporting Events'.
- ²⁵ Scott-Parker and Zadek, 'Managing Diversity', 120. See also Zadek and Scott-Parker, 'Unlocking Potential'.
- ²⁶ Luker, 'Why Sport Industry must Recognize Importance of Older Fans'.
- ²⁷ Ibid., 120.
- ²⁸ Ibid., 120.
- ²⁹ Eurostat, *Demography Report 2010; Active Ageing and Solidarity between Generations; Basic Figures on the EU*.
- ³⁰ Eurostat, *Active Ageing and Solidarity between Generations*, 15. Similar demographic projections are provided by the Office for National (UK) Statistics where it is stated that the UK population will increase from 62.3 m. in 2010 to reach 70 m. by mid-2027 with the average (median) age rising from 39.7 years in 2010 to 39.9 years in 2020 to 42.2 by 2035 (See more at the Office for National Statistics, *National Population Projections*). Beyond Europe, the U.S. Census Bureau states that the 65 years and over population grew at a faster rate than the total population. Trend that it will continue to rise in the next decades (See more at Werner, *The Older Population: 2010*).
- ³¹ Ahtonen and Pardo, 'The Accessibility Act'.
- ³² *Department for Work & Pensions, Fulfilling Potential*, VI.
- ³³ Office for Disability Issues, *Growing your Customer Base to Include Disabled People*, 5.
- ³⁴ Spanish Statistics Institute, *Spain in Figures 2013*.
- ³⁵ Eurostat, *Demography Report 2010; Active Ageing and Solidarity between Generations; Basic Figures on the EU*.
- ³⁶ Ahtonen and Pardo, 'The Accessibility Act'.
- ³⁷ Waterman and Bell, *Disabled Access to Facilities*.
- ³⁸ Grady and Paramio-Salcines, 'Global Approaches to Managing the Fan Experience for Patrons with Disabilities'. Grady and Paramio-Salcines 'Global Disability Laws and their Impact on the Stadium Experience'.
- ³⁹ CAFÉ, *Annual Report 2011-2012*. Similar argument can be found in UEFAa. *Access for All. UEFA and CAFÉ Good Practice Guide to Creating an Accessible Stadium and Matchday Experience*, 10.
- ⁴⁰ Taylor, *Torkildsen's Sport and Leisure Management*, 42.
- ⁴¹ García Ferrando and Llopis Goig. *Ideal democrático y bienestar personal: Encuesta sobre hábitos deportivos en España 2010*.
- ⁴² CAFÉ, *Annual Report 2011-2012*.
- ⁴³ See Reiche 'Drivers behind Corporate Social Responsibility in the Professional Football Sector: A case study of the German Bundesliga'.
- ⁴⁴ Premier League, *2012/13 Premier League Season Review*, 7.
- ⁴⁵ See more details in Paramio, Campos and Buraimo, 'Promoting Accessibility for Fans with Disabilities to European Stadiums and Arenas'; Paramio-Salcines and Kitchin, 'Institutional Perspectives on the Implementation of Disability Legislation and Services for Spectators with Disabilities in European Professional Football'.
- ⁴⁶ Premier League, *2012/13 Premier League Season Review*, 29.
- ⁴⁷ Level Playing Field, *Annual Report 2012/2013*.

⁴⁸ As the Manchester United Foundation impact report 2012/13 stressed, the club, through Manchester United Disabled Supporters Association (MUDSA), provided nearly 10,000 (9,831) tickets for disabled supporters and their caregivers for the season 2012/13. Additionally, an increasing number of children and adults with disabilities engaged in different disability programs as Ability Counts in the club since 2000. In particular, 156 players were registered on the Ability Counts program. See more details at Downs and Paramio-Salcines, 'Incorporating Accessibility and Disability in the Manchester United Culture and Organization as part of their CSR policies' and Manchester United Foundation. *A Season Review. Taking Manchester United to the Heart of the Community. Impact Report 2012/13.*

⁴⁹ Paramio-Salcines et al., 'Disability Provision in European stadia within a CSR framework'; Paramio, Campos and Buraimo, 'Promoting Accessibility for Fans with Disabilities to European Stadiums and Arenas'.

⁵⁰ Ibid.

⁵¹ See FC Barcelona. Presentació Web Accessible.

⁵² See more details of the provision for fans with disabilities at top main stadia of the Spanish Primera Division, Bundesliga and Premier League's clubs as well as the new Wembley Stadium at Paramio, Campos and Buraimo, 'Promoting Accessibility for Fans with Disabilities to European Stadiums and Arenas: A Holistic Journey Sequence Approach', 380-383.

⁵³ Taylor, *Torkildsen's Sport and Leisure Management.*

⁵⁴ Ibid., 63.

⁵⁵ Office for Disability Issues, 'Growing your Customer Base to Include Disabled People', 5; Waterman and Bell, *Disabled Access to Facilities*; Scott-Parker and Zadek, 'Managing Diversity'; Zadek and Scott-Parker. 'Unlocking Potential'.

⁵⁶ Level Playing Field, *Annual Report 2012/2013.*

⁵⁷ Brault, *American with Disabilities: 2010.*

⁵⁸ U.S. Department of Justice, *Accessibility Benefits Older Adult Customers.*

⁵⁹ Paramio-Salcines and Kitchin, 'Institutional Perspectives on the Implementation of Disability Legislation and Services for Spectators with Disabilities in European Professional Football'.

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